

BONDED COMPOSITE PATCH TO REPAIR METALLIC STRUCTURES: FATIGUE BEHAVIOUR OF A DISBOND

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SUMMARY

The main difficulty for the use of composite patches to repair damaged metallic structures is the lack of confidence in the bond. One possibility is to adopt a damage tolerance approach for the disbond. In that frame, this study gives a model of the disbond propagation, the law being obtained by test results.

Keywords: Aeronautical Repair, bonded composite patch, fatigue behaviour.

GENERAL CONTEXT

Context

Like many others, the French Ministry of Defence is facing the challenge of ageing aircraft in its inventory. Corrosion and fatigue cracking are the main sources of damages in these airframes. Most of the time, a repair to restore the structural integrity is necessary.

Most of conventional repair techniques of fatigue damages consist in fastened metallic doublers. They require the drilling of the metallic structure in areas which are already affected by fatigue concerns. New cracks may appear in these areas which became consequently difficult to inspect.

The concept of a composite patch bonded on the damaged structure has been studied and applied in Australia more than thirty years ago [1]. It offers many advantages such as a smoother load transfer, the possibility to use thin and stiff repairs, its formability that allows low-cost manufacture for fabrication. We can also mention the fact that only one side of the structure needs to be physically accessible and that the temporary use of that repair is possible without irreversible consequences (new hole drilled). However, this repair raises some concerns: the residual stress induced by the differences between metallic and composite thermal dilatation coefficients, the effect of casual in-service temperature and humidity on the properties of both composite and adhesive, but also the high secondary bending effect.

Today the efficiency of the load by-pass and therefore of crack retardation is well demonstrated but the use of this repair technique is limited by the lack of confidence in the bond as single load path for primary and even secondary aeronautical structures. The inability to assess the reliability of a bonding is the main difficulty to overcome in order to let a bonded patch fly. In that context, qualitative and quantitative information on the

initiation and the propagation of a disbond between the metal and the composite patch will be helpful for the decisions of the authorities on repair technique validation.

Strategy for bonding assessment

Our test centre is performing tests to characterise the fatigue behaviour of the adhesive between a composite patch and a metallic substrate. The idea is to increase our experience but also to be able to transpose to other situation. Basically, the bond is controllable by NDI. The questions are: is a disbond which would be detected dangerous for the structural integrity? Can a periodical inspection of the bond be defined in order to ensure that a sudden unsafe debonding will not occur?

A possible approach is to study the debonding in the same manner as a crack with the linear fracture mechanics theory. It can be done based on the common modelling means for composite patch repair put in place for previous studies [2]. In [3], the authors have concluded that the governing parameter was the global energy release rate.

The present study carries out the modelling necessary to determine the energy release rate linked to a given increase of the disbond size. These computation tools correlated with test results will enable to determine a propagation law similar to Paris ones

$\frac{da}{dN} = C(\Delta G)^n$ for the crack propagation in metallic substrate. This will be the first step to fulfil a damage tolerance approach for patch debonding. Roughly speaking, it consists in assuming an existent damage and in determining an inspection program which enable to detect the disbond before it became critical. It means also that effective non destructive techniques exist.

Our objective is not to use this prediction tool systematically to design the repair but rather to reassure the technical authorities towards the consequences of an unexpected initiation of a disbond and its potential hazardous growth. Indeed the scepticism against bonded repair endures because the environmental effect on bonded joints is not well established and safety margins must therefore be taken.

Study development

The problem is to deal with the fatigue of a bonded joint. The scope of the study is only fatigue behaviour. It means that the bonded joint is supposed to have been well designed, i.e. the current load does not pass the yield stress, and only the repetition of the loads possibly causes damages in the structure.

The first part of the study will be the experimental determination of the fatigue propagation law. In that purpose, coupons with a special geometry have been manufactured and tested in fatigue. It enables to measure the disbond area growth during the fatigue test. Then the correlated energy release rate has to be determined. In that purpose, a simple modelling of the test is performed. Based on energy balance, it enables to compute the energy release rates corresponding to the applied load. Once the propagation law obtained, it is then possible to model the propagation of a disbond on a realistic patched configuration. These results are finally compared with other fatigue tests on representative coupons.

TEST CAMPAIGN TO OBTAIN THE PROPAGATION LAW

Geometry of the coupons

The design is the DOFS (double overlap-joint fatigue specimen, see [1]). They are manufactured by bonding symmetrically the outer composite plates ($0^\circ/90^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ$) to two along side 3 mm thick aluminium (2024-T351) plates with adhesive Redux 312 (Figure 1). The width of the specimen is 24 mm. The surface treatment, preceding the bonding, is the one performed for structural bonding, with the scoring of the surface and the use of Silane primer. The cure was performed at 120°C in an autoclave. Teflon films were introduced to create an initial disbond but also to avoid any friction between the composite and the aluminium during the test. Stepping is applied at the extremities of the composite patch to avoid debonding at this location.

Figure 1: test coupon scheme and picture.

This specimen geometry has numerous advantages. Firstly, the loading mode is quite close to the composite patched structure one. Secondly the size of the disbond is directly measurable by an extensometer between the regarding aluminium faces. The entire load has to pass through the composite at the centre of the specimen. Assuming that the adhesive shear strain γ is uniform (ignoring the crack tip singularity) the displacement δ is simply:

$$\delta = 2 \cdot \gamma \cdot t_A + 2 \cdot b \cdot \varepsilon_0$$

Where t_A is the thickness of the adhesive, b is the disbond length and ε_0 the maximum longitudinal strain in the composite at the centre of the patch (cf. Figure 2).

Figure 2: disbond length measurement

Thus there is an affine relationship between the disbond length and the measured displacement.

Test process

The specimen is loaded in traction through the aluminium at its extremities. The displacement δ is measured by extensometer (see Figure 3). Four coupons have been tested at different load levels. The test consists in a simple sinusoidal fatigue test with monotonous constant amplitude loading with an aspect ratio between the minimum applied load and the maximum of 0.1. Acquisitions of the displacement values are made at one peak-valley over hundred.

Figure 3: fatigue test facility.

As the relationship between the disbond length b and the measured displacement δ does not depend on b , several load levels can be applied one after another on the same coupon. Different load levels between 30 MPa and 170 MPa have been investigated. Generally 20 000 cycles by load levels have been applied until 130 MPa, and fewer beyond (Figure 4).

Figure 4: typical applied load schedule.

Results

Once the test performed, the ratio $\frac{\delta}{2 \cdot \varepsilon_0}$ is computed. Then the derivative $\frac{db}{dN}$ is computed by searching the best linear approximation of b vs. number of load cycles curve at each load level. It is performed using the least square method. As the precision of the sensor is 0.01 mm, all load levels which did not results in an total increase of the measured displacement of less than 0.01 mm have been rejected. It corresponds to all the load levels below 95 MPa.

Then the results are converted in increased disbond areas multiplying the results by the width of the specimen. The results of the disbond area per load cycle vs. energy release rate are plotted in a logarithmic scale (cf. Figure 5).

Figure 5: disbond propagation law interpolation.

We can notice that there is a good linearity of the results. The interpolation line equation is represented. It results in the following propagation law:

$$\frac{dA}{dN} = 1.09 \cdot 10^{-14} (G)^{4,60}.$$

Where A is the disbond area, N the number of load cycles.

For comparison the same test has been performed on coupons where the composite patch has been bonded without Silane primer. It represents downgraded bonding conditions.

Figure 6: test results of downgraded bonding conditions.

The results (Figure 6) are roughly similar to the previous ones. The propagation is only slightly faster. The reason is that, with or without Silane, the debonding is essentially adhesive at the interface between the adhesive and the composite patch. Therefore there is only few influence of the adhesive property at the metallic-bond interface.

MODELLING

General modelling

The main objective is to explain the computation of the energy release rate corresponding to observed disbond propagation during tests and used previously. For further application, it is important to be able to predict disbond propagation on more realistic structures. The chosen model should also be put in place easily. The study of propagation imposes moreover that all the models are parameterized to be compatible with an evolving geometry. All the modelling will be performed using Samcef Bacon.

Another point is that the adhesive is 0.125 mm thick, which is relatively small in comparison with the specimen length * width (200*24 mm). To have precisely the stress in the adhesive and to avoid a too refined mesh, interface elements have been chosen. As they are only suitable with volume elements, the composite is modelled in volumes and orthotropic material. Interface elements in Samcef consist in duplicating the nodes of the considered surface and introducing three unidirectional springs to model the peeling action σ_{zz} and two shears stresses σ_{xz} and σ_{yz} . The debonded area is obtained by first creating the interface elements and then removing them progressively so as to let two coincident unconnected nodes.

A particularity of the bonding between aluminium and composite is the thermal residual stresses. This stress level is comparable to the one applied mechanically and therefore cannot be neglected. Different computation strategies have been intended. As material non linearity of the adhesive was not possible to investigate, it was chosen to remain linear in our computation.

Geometry, hypothesis and boundary conditions

As mentioned above, all the computations are made assuming linear behaviour. The material characteristics are described Table 1.

Table 1 : material characteristics.

	Aluminium 2024 T 351	Composite Carbone/epoxy ply	Composite Verre/epoxy ply	Adhesive Redux 312
E_x (MPa)	72000	141300	40000	1800
E_y (MPa)	72000	9300	8000	1800
E_z (MPa)	72000	9300	8000	1800
G (MPa)		5500	9000	
ν	0,33	0,3	0,26	0,33
α_x (C° ⁻¹)	$2,3 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$-4,5 \cdot 10^{-7}$	$3,5 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$2,3 \cdot 10^{-5}$
α_y (C° ⁻¹)	$2,3 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$2,8 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$2,8 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$2,3 \cdot 10^{-5}$
α_z (C° ⁻¹)	$2,3 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$2,8 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$3,5 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$2,3 \cdot 10^{-5}$
ρ	2,8	1,6	1,6	1

For symmetry reasons, only an eighth of the coupons is modelled (see Figure 7) when the specimen is patched on both sides and one quarter when only one side is patched.

Figure 7: mesh of coupons.

To improve the visibility of the adhesive for post-processing, the composite has been offset so that the disbond as well as the results in the bonded joint can be observed. All the elements are quadrangles. The disbond front has been slightly refined. The basic coupons have been loaded with imposed pressure on the extremity face.

Energy release rate computation

The energy release rate is obtained by an energy balance of the global system [4]. With an increase of the debonded area of dA , the creation of a new crack or disbond results in an irreversible dissipation of energy. Thus the energy release rate G is given by:

$$G = - \frac{d}{dS} (U - W)$$

U is the stored elastic energy and W the external work.

Considering the process as isothermal and assuming the linearity we can transform the expression of U by using integral transformation, it becomes:

$$G = -\frac{d}{dS} \left(\frac{1}{2} \left(\int_{\Sigma} (T \cdot \xi^d - T^d \cdot \xi) da \right) \right)$$

ξ^d and T^d being respectively the imposed displacement and load on the external surface Σ of the structure.

According to the previous equation, to compute the energy release rate, only the stress and strain at the model border is needed. Indeed, it concerns the reactions at the nodes where displacements are applied, and the displacements of the nodes where the pressure is applied.

Concerning the residual thermal stress, a specific load case is created. This load case, cooling from 120°C to 20°C, is taken as the initial state (I). Then two other load cases are computed. The first one (F1) corresponds to the combination of thermal and mechanical loads for a given disbond. The second one (F2) has an increased disbond area and the same thermo-mechanical load.

(U – W) is computed between I and F1 and then between the same I and F2. These two values correspond to the two following possibilities: Either the disbond remains stable or it grows during the load application. G is simply the ratio of the energies by the increase of the disbond surface. This method enables easily to take into account the initial thermal residual state and to compare both potential energy levels associated to F1 and F2.

The sources of errors are multiple. Firstly finite elements method principle is to approximate the stress and the strain fields. Thus, changing the mesh will have an impact on the results for computational reasons. In our case, the disbond growth forced to modify the mesh, which disrupted the results. In this study, it has been verified that refining the mesh has only a slight influence on the results. Secondly, for tiny disbond growth, the difference of energy can be comparable to the incertitude on results. To minimize this problem, the disbond size perturbation has been fitted at 0.25 mm. Then, from a theoretical point of view, a part of the dissipated energy is stored in plastic deformation at the crack front. In our case, it is acceptable to neglect it since there is no real stress field singularity at the crack tip. Nevertheless, plasticity cannot yet be taken into account for materials compatible with interface elements on Samcef. Finally, for shear loading, there is some energy dissipating by friction between the regarding disbond faces. Due to the complexity of the involved shapes, it is not possible to take it into account.

VALIDATION ON REPRESENTATIVE COUPONS

Coupons geometry

Those coupons (see Figure 8) are cut in 1.6 mm thick sheets of aluminium 2024-T351. The design in “wasp waist” enables to introduce high loads without breaking the specimen in the load introduction areas.

The standard patch geometry is one-sided, elliptical shaped with stepping. The first coupons used those kinds of patch (Figure 8a). A bond defect was introduced by

replacing locally the adhesive with a circular piece of protective film (white circle on the patch). The disbond growth is controlled periodically by ultrasonic non destructive inspection. This can be done without removing the coupon from the test facilities. The potential disbond growth is measured with a precision of about 1mm. Under the patch, the metal is undamaged to avoid any interactions which would be difficult to analyse. This configuration is representative of a repaired aeronautical structure.

Unfortunately for our study, no disbond propagation occurred for 10 000 000 load cycles at 175 MPa (constant loading ratio $R = 0.1$) in the central area, for those types of patch. Increasing the load level only caused the failure of the specimen in the metal part (Figure 8b). Four different initial disbond locations have been investigated. Two in the central area and two at the edge (up and lateral). No difference was made between them.

Figure 8: representative coupons (a, b and c)

After that, a static test of traction was performed on a one side patched specimen with an initial disbond at the upper edge of the patch. Wide debonding suddenly occurs at 405 MPa in the central zone of the coupons. Almost half of the patch did disbond, but it was at a load level far beyond the yield stress of the aluminium (about 340 MPa) and this test result is therefore useless for the modelling of fatigue damage. The static limit being too far from the possible applied load levels, we decided to change the geometry of the patch to make the configuration more critical for the adhesive. Therefore the patch definition has progressively evolved. In that process, no difference was made by removing the stepping, or double-siding the circular patch.

Finally, a lozenge shaped composite patch was bonded symmetrically on both sides of the metal sheet. It presents both advantages of being, for a given stress level, more critical for the adhesive due to the sharp edge and less for the metallic part due to a smoother load transfer. Double-siding the patch cancel the secondary bending effect, and therefore the associated bending in the aluminium and the compressive stress in the adhesive. With that configuration, debonding was obtained between 225 and 275 MPa for some of the coupons. Nevertheless all the tests have been interrupted by breaking of the coupons in the metal part (cf. Figure 8 c), but at higher cycle numbers.

Model

This model uses the same approach than the previous one. The interface elements have been used. The shape of the disbond is assumed to be and to remain circular. As previously, for symmetry reasons, only one eighth of the specimen is modelled. As a consequence of the use of symmetry, the propagation is assumed to be symmetrical between the corners of the patch. An imposed displacement is applied at the edge of the coupon (cf. Figure 9). The mesh is obtained by extrusion.

Figure 9: coupon model.

The stress results are used to verify that the stress level in the adhesive has not exceeded the yield stress of the Redux 312 (37 MPa). Besides, they show that there is a peel stress peak in the sharp edge of the remaining adhesive (see Figure 10). This zone is the preferential location of the observed disbond during the tests.

Figure 10: peel stress and shear in the adhesive.

Results

Indeed among eight coupons, only two gave propagation results. After the four initial already mentioned, one met premature failure, and one debonded during the last load cycles so that it was impossible to reject the hypothesis that it only appeared during the coupons break. On the two remaining coupons, measurable propagation occurs. Several propagation rates were found and correlated to the energy release rates computed by the model. All the results are summarized Figure 11.

Figure 11: test propagation results in comparison with propagation law.

The correlation between the test results on representative coupons and the propagation law previously computed is not good and, even worse, underestimated. Several reasons can explain that:

- Errors in the computation of energy release rate, especially because it is based on an assumption of circular propagation.
- The fact that the propagation during test is not symmetrical between the different corners of the patch. It results in wrong energy release rates computations.
- The measurement of the disbond, which is performed by ultrasonic non destructive inspection. The precision of the measures is about 1mm only, which is quite poor and the interval of inspection was 10 000 cycles at least.
- The geometry of the glue joint at the border of the patch, which disrupts the propagation.

Globally, the sources of errors must lead to an underestimation of the energy release rate. Consequently, the correction of these points should result in an increase of G , which is coherent with the position of the pink points of Figure 11 as compared to the propagation law. Therefore, these “bad” results do not necessary cast doubts on the general method used and there is a real hope of validating the approach after correction of the model.

The final objective was to anticipate a disbond of an adhesive joint. In that purpose, we have computed with the presented tools the propagation of the disbond with the load applied to one of the coupons where debonding occurred. From the applied load, we computed corresponding energy release rates, then the disbond area increase and finally the new radius. Everything was performed with an Excel sheet. The comparison between modelling and results is presented Figure 12. The 3 000 000 loads cycles gives no disbond growth either by test or computation.

Figure 12: propagation of a disbond: comparison between test and modelling.

There is not a really good correlation but the trends seem globally coherent. More tests results would be necessary to validate the results taking into account the experience feedback on first tests. Several points are not taken into account. Particularly, an assumption of the model is that the disbond shape remains circular. During tests, it is rapidly not the case anymore. The disbond grows firstly at the critical area. It results in a cauliflower shape for the disbond (cf. Figure 13). Correlating it with an energy release rate computed for a circular shape is source of errors.

Figure 13: observed “cauliflower shaped” evolution of a disbond.

Unfortunately, even if it is possible to better correlate after test by reproducing the exact shape of the disbond, it is another problem to be able to anticipate the phenomenon and our final objective is to have a prediction tool.

CONCLUSION

The objective was to test and model the propagation of a disbond under a composite patch used to repair a metallic structure. It can enable to predict the number of load cycles the structure is able to sustain without dramatic consequences. In that purpose, a test campaign was performed to assess the propagation rate. A simple modelling, using

interface elements and a method of computing the energy release rate was defined. It enables to compute the energy release rates correlated to the observed propagation. From that, it was possible to estimate a propagation law similar to Paris one for the propagation of cracks in a metallic structure.

The obtained law was used to predict the propagation of a disbond on a more complex and representative coupons. The results are correct but not totally accurate and cannot at this stage be used with sufficient confidence. Several difficulties appeared and some of them have not been solved yet. For example, the shape evolutions do not remain the one assumed and there are numbers of disbond propagation locations.

At the moment, there is a lack of usable test results to really validate or reject the obtained tool. Therefore a new test campaign has been launched to add data to our basis. Moreover, it will be interesting to deal with downgraded bond process, with bad surface preparation to characterize the deterioration of the bond durability. In fact, knockdown factors will be necessary to take into account all the environmental conditions which can alter the adhesive properties.

During the repair design stage, the damage tolerance approach will not necessary be used for all the part of the patch. As proposed by A. Baker in [1], for sensible zones, at the edge of the patch, the design must fulfil safe life requirements. Nevertheless, it can be used for the centre of the patch where a disbond is often appearing but also where it is less critical for the integrity of the repair. Moreover, the lack of knowledge on bond durability made any information on the behaviour of the adhesive in fatigue is valuable.

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